

Section 1: Applicants

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Organisation	Amsterdam UMC

Name of the cooperation partner (person)	Dr. L. Ingeborgh van den Born
E-mail address	[Redacted]
Organisation	Rotterdam Eye Hospital

Name of the cooperation partner (person)	Dr. Dun Jack Fu
E-mail address	[Redacted]
Organisation	Moorfields Eye Hospital NHS / University College London

Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	National Infrastructure for Ophthalmic Imaging
Project duration (in months)	48 months

English public summary

Eye research and AI innovation in the Netherlands are world-class, but progress is held back by a lack of infrastructure to share medical images and AI tools across institutions. Eye diseases are extensively imaged using diverse, high-resolution techniques, producing data with immense potential for advancing diagnosis, prognosis, and therapy. Yet, these images are stored in incompatible systems, leaving data fragmented. This project will build a secure, national platform to collect, harmonize, and share multimodal eye images and AI modules. It will enable open, collaborative research and accelerate scientific discovery—while ensuring that patient privacy is protected.

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 96

Dutch public summary

Nederland loopt voorop in oogheelkundig onderzoek en AI-ontwikkeling, maar het ontbreken van een gedeelde infrastructuur voor medische beelddata belemmert wetenschappelijke vooruitgang. Oogziekten worden routinematig vastgelegd met geavanceerde, multimodale beeldvorming die cruciaal is voor het ontwikkelen van AI-modellen voor diagnose, prognose en therapie. Deze data blijven nu vaak opgesloten in gefragmenteerde en niet-compatibele systemen. Dit project realiseert een nationale infrastructuur voor het veilig verzamelen, standaardiseren en delen van oogheelkundige beelden en AI-modules. Hiermee versterken we de wetenschappelijke positie van Nederland en versnellen we innovatie, met blijvende waarborgen voor privacy en data-integriteit.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 90

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

Ophthalmology currently relies on vendor-specific systems to store eye images, which severely limits interoperability and data sharing. At Erasmus MC, we developed the EyeNED platform for image storage, visualization, annotation, and AI modelling for research purposes, but it is not yet widely adopted. Health-RI offers national infrastructure and services for FAIR research data, but these are not adapted to ophthalmic data formats. Grand Challenge is a widely used open platform for training and benchmarking AI models on medical images, yet integration with Dutch ophthalmology datasets remains limited.

The goal of this project is to develop a national, open infrastructure for data sharing, annotation, and AI development in Ophthalmology. We will provide EyeNED as a cloud service within the Health-RI ecosystem, integrate it with existing tools, and leverage its legal governance framework. We will also connect EyeNED to Grand Challenge for algorithm evaluation and AI collaboration across disciplines and borders.

By **linking EyeNED with Health-RI and Grand Challenge**, we will create essential infrastructure that provides eye researchers access to curated and FAIRified data pipelines for AI development and validation, enabling open, cross-institutional collaboration and accelerating scientific discovery and innovation.

Fig. 1: Visualization of different centres sharing data in the envisioned infrastructure.

Word count SEC31 (max. 200): 195

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

Eye professionals typically rely on proprietary imaging software with limited interoperability, often using a separate system for each imaging device. Lack of infrastructure and technical expertise restricts adoption of vendor-neutral archives and DICOM standards^{1,2,3}. This results in significant barriers in accessing, sharing, and reusing data and algorithms. Existing Health-RI tools do not yet support the imaging formats and workflow specific to ophthalmology, which we address in this proposal.

For researchers in the eye field, the challenge lies in the lack of open tools for exploring, annotating, and extracting quantitative outcomes from ophthalmic images. Current open solutions are not tailored to common modalities such as OCT and OCTA, or measurements like retinal layer segmentations. Hence, researchers remain dependent on proprietary software. This proposal introduces tools that support effective curation while ensuring (meta)data are FAIR and open by design – maximizing reuse and discovery.

AI developers, academic and commercial, need curated and expert-annotated data sets to train, validate, and benchmark their models. The proposed infrastructure addresses this by creating an open ecosystem for transparent and reproducible AI development.

Data stewards & privacy officers need tools that support data reuse within legal and ethical boundaries. This project links technical infrastructure to a robust governance framework, which includes a national consortium agreement for Dutch Ophthalmology.

By linking existing platforms and tools, the proposed infrastructure streamlines collaboration between clinicians, researchers, developers, and support roles like data managers and policy officers. Researchers gain access to high-quality, reusable data and tools for developing and validating AI. Patients benefit from improved care, with their data contributing to science in a transparent and secure way.

Figure 2: Illustration of needs addressed by this proposal.

Word count SEC32 (max. 300): 300

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

The infrastructure developed in this proposal supports a transformation to open science practices throughout the community by:

- Supporting data FAIRification and sharing
- Contributing to the ecosystem of open-source software and standards
- Building an open community and being transparent in our decision-making

Data FAIRification and sharing

Data stored in the infrastructure will be FAIR by design and sharing will be simplified through the legal framework and cloud platform. Protocols for data import, annotation, model evaluation, and export will be fully documented and accessible through open APIs and data standards such as [DICOM](#) and [OMOP](#). This ensures that data can be indexed by data catalogues and exchanged with other systems.

Open-source software and standards

An open-source infrastructure will reduce reliance on proprietary software and promote open innovation. The infrastructure will support integration with commercial and academic tools through open standards, promoting fair competition and interoperability. The Grand Challenge platform facilitates benchmarking of AI algorithms, fostering transparent development and reproducible science.

Community building and transparency

A core goal is to foster an open and inclusive user community. We will seek constant feedback from users and remain transparent about our decision-making with regards to supported data formats and features. Therefore, we will publish our development roadmap and provide regular updates on our progress through the online repository, a website and newsletter. There will be regular opportunities to raise questions and provide input during live sessions at national and international conferences and through public channels such as GitHub issues. We will engage with other open-source initiatives and collaborate where possible.

Word count SEC33 (max. 300): 255

3.4 Access policy

All software developed in this project will be published with an open-source license. The cloud services will be accessible through the existing policies of Health-RI. It is designed as both a federated and central architecture, so participating institutes can use the central cloud services or set up a local node. The cloud services are offered with a not-for-profit pricing model that covers operating costs.

Figure 3: Ways to use infrastructure.

The consortium agreement will be open-ended, meaning that institutes can join the consortium at any time by signing the agreement. Access to individual datasets is decided by the data holders. It can be restricted to a specific set of collaborators, completely open, or public with a license agreement to comply with ELSI requirements. The same policy will apply to algorithms. Health-RI has a [servicedesk](#) to facilitate the process of gaining access to all elements of the infrastructure.

Word count SEC34 (max. 150): 150

3.5 (Inter)national ecosystem

Health-RI is part of the National Roadmap for Large-Scale Research Infrastructure, and through it we will connect to health data beyond imaging (e.g. [Molgenis](#)). This proposal involves participation from leading ophthalmology centres and algorithm developers. The ongoing Lifelong Vision Consortium (NWO Gravitation, 2024-2034) will be users of the infrastructure, ensuring adoption by the community.

At the European level, the upcoming European Health Data Space (EHDS) will mandate improved accessibility and interoperability of health data. The infrastructure developed in this project will complement it. Specifically, we envision that the developed tools will be available within the Secure Processing Environments outlined by the EHDS, enabling more advanced analysis of ophthalmic imaging data.

Internationally, we will—where possible—align with or draw inspiration from initiatives such as EyeGENE⁴, AI-READI⁵, and [SOIN](#), which contribute valuable insights into data standards and federated sharing. However, these infrastructures do not provide a comprehensive technical solution to the needs addressed in this proposal. Our existing tools are already embraced by international collaborators, including Moorfields Reading Centre. Open standards for ophthalmology data are being developed in the [OHDSI Eye Care and Vision working group](#), in which we are actively involved.

Figure 4: Overview of connected initiatives.

Word count SEC35 (max. 200): 197

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

We will achieve our results through the following workpackages:

Figure 5: Overview of workpackages

WP1 Extraction and harmonization

We will design and implement ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) pipelines to gather imaging data from clinical systems, apply any necessary transformation and send them to a vendor-neutral database (e.g. [XNAT](#)). They will be designed in a modular way and delivered with a user manual and developer documentation. We will build upon or contribute to existing solutions where possible (e.g. [CTP](#), [OCTconverter](#)).

The transformations include:

- Conversion of proprietary standards to DICOM
- Anonymization and removal of sensitive data
- Ensuring that key metadata is included and standardized (e.g. localization)

WP2 Curation and annotation

The EyeNED platform is an open-source research PACS for ophthalmology that enables data curation and (AI-assisted) annotation. It provides essential domain-specific features such as ETDRS grid placement, image registration, OCT enface projection and layer segmentation. In this task we will develop the platform towards a future-proof, modular and extensible system that can be deployed in the cloud and connected to the other data storages (e.g. XNAT).

The main tasks will be to:

- Develop a cloud implementation
- Facilitate integration with other data sources
- Implement authentication through SURFConext
- Improve modularity, extensibility and documentation

Figure 6: Screenshots of the EyeNED platform. A) Image browsing; B) Vascular segmentation; C) ETDRS grid placement and image registration; D) OCT enface projection and layer segmentation

WP 3 Algorithm Integration and export

AI algorithms are increasingly important for biomarker extraction and data curation. In this task we will integrate the EyeNED platform with [Grand Challenge](#) (GC), where challenges or benchmarks can be hosted and algorithms can be deployed and exchanged. We will:

- Offer a seamless integration to run algorithms through API calls
- Enable export of curated datasets to GC to create benchmarks, or any other repository such as [Zenodo](#) for persistent storage

Hereby we leverage the complementary features of both systems.

Figure 7. Interconnection between data sources and platforms.

WP4 Use cases and outreach

Task 4.1: Testing data ingestion

We will test the ETL pipelines at different centres to provide essential feedback. We leverage existing collaborations by using data from the RD-5000 cohort of patients with inherited retinal dystrophies. This will include emerging modalities such as adaptive optics flood illumination ophthalmoscopy (AO-FIO) and microperimetry. We will onboard Eye Hospital Rotterdam, RadboudUMC, EMC and Amsterdam UMC in this task.

Task 4.2: Testing annotation and algorithms

This task will demonstrate the platform's utility to curate large datasets through user interaction and algorithms. We will import imaging data from the Maastricht Study into the PACS and apply a series of open-source algorithms developed at EMC for:

- Automated quality assessment
- Retinal layer segmentation
- Vascular analysis

The results will be reviewed by graders at the EyeNED Reading Center, who will provide feedback on the usability of the platform. This will be a showcase of the potential of our infrastructure to generate high-quality FAIR data.

Task 4.3: Outreach

To ensure wide community adoption, we will connect to the community through multiple channels by:

- Presenting the infrastructure at the national ophthalmology conference (NOG) and organizing a workshop for potential users.
- Showcasing the infrastructure at the leading international conference in ophthalmology (ARVO) to promote international adoption and collaboration
- Publishing a roadmap and regular updates online and in a newsletter
- Visiting local centres for user instruction

The goal is to onboard at least two additional projects and generate interest from international collaborators to use and contribute to our tools.

WP5 Sustainability and governance

Task 5.1: ELSI

Health-RI already provides guidance for researchers through the ELSI servicedesk. We will assess the existing regulatory framework and set up a consortium agreement between participating centres and Health-RI to cover additional needs. We will ensure provisions for future inclusion of additional parties and for sharing outside the consortium, including with commercial parties. The aim is being as open as possible while protecting the rights of patients and considering the needs of all stakeholders (researchers, clinicians, companies). We will assess the impact of EHDS on the regulatory framework as it becomes clear during the project.

Task 5.2: Sustainability

We will work together with Health-RI to incorporate the EyeNED platform as a service and establish a maintenance plan. We will discuss with the national ophthalmology society (NOG) how to support this work beyond the duration of the project and seek structural funding for software development.

Table 1: Timeline

	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4
WP1				
WP2				
WP3				
T4.1				
T4.2				
T4.3				
T5.1				
T5.3				

Word count SEC 41 (max. 750): 735

4.2 Team composition

Name, surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
Dr. K.A. van Garderen	EMC	Postdoc, AI developer, project manager	Project manager, organizing outreach activities and coordinating WP5. Task 4.1 co-coordinator
Prof.dr. C.C.W. Klaver	EMC, Radboudumc	Full professor ophthalmology & epidemiology, Lead PI Lifelong Vision Consortium	PI WP4, Lifelong Vision Liaison
Dr. S. Klein	EMC, Health-RI	Associate professor in applied medical image analysis, Health-RI Imaging lead	PI WP5, Health-RI Liaison
Prof.dr. C. Sanchez	UvA	Full professor AI in medical imaging, PI Lifelong Vision, contributor to Grand Challenge	PI WP3
Dr. H. Achterberg	EMC	Senior research software engineer	PI & senior developer WP1
Dr. B. Liefers	EMC	Senior research software engineer	PI & senior developer WP2
Dr. ir. Danilo Andrade De Jesus	EMC, Eye Hospital Rotterdam	Assistant professor AI in ophthalmology	Task 4.1 co-coordinator
Dr. Luisa Sánchez Brea	EMC, Eye Hospital Rotterdam	Assistant professor AI in ophthalmology	Task 4.2 co-coordinator
Dr.ir. Jose Vargas Quiros	EMC	Postdoc, AI developer	Task 4.2 co-coordinator
	EMC	Graders at EyeNED Reading Centre	Task 4.2 retinal grading
	UvA	Senior research software engineer	Senior developer WP3
	EMC	Research software engineer	WP1 software development
	EMC	Research software engineer	WP2 software development
	UvA	Research software engineer	WP3 software development
THIRD PARTIES			
	Contracted through EMC	Legal expert	Task 5.1 drafting consortium agreement
	SURF	Cloud consultant	advice on cloud implementation WP2
COOPERATION PARTNERS			
Dr. Tos Berendschot	Maastricht UMC+	Associate professor Ophthalmic Physics	Clinical partner Maastricht study
Prof.dr. Camiel Boon	Amsterdam UMC	Full professor clinical ophthalmogenetics	Clinical partner RD5000
Dr. L. Ingeborgh van den Born	Eye Hospital Rotterdam	Clinical manager Rotterdam Ophthalmic Institute, Co-founder RD5000	Clinical partner RD5000
Dr. Dun Jack Fu	Moorfields Eye Hospital NHS / University College London	Team lead at Moorfields Reading Centre	Collaborator in joint development of EyeNED platform

Word count SEC42 (max. 350): 285

4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
We are not able to deal with the wide variety of imaging modalities and devices	Likelihood: high Impact: medium	We maintain a documentation of the various formats and document the degree of support and remaining challenges for future work.
Different institutes cannot agree on the terms of the consortium agreement.	Likelihood: low Impact: medium	If no consortium agreement is in place, institutes can still rely on the ELSI servicedesk of Health-RI and implement bilateral agreements where needed.
Elements of the central infrastructure are too costly	Likelihood: low Impact: medium	If users are not able to carry the cost of the central infrastructure, they have the option to run the software locally. This we will actively support through documentation.
No sustainable model is found to maintain development of the software	Likelihood: low Impact: high	Development of the software so far has been funded on a project basis. We will fall back on this strategy if no structural funding is found.
Elements of the infrastructure become obsolete due to other technological developments	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	The participating groups are well connected among other groups developing software in medical imaging. We will keep track of developments, partner with other projects and use existing or emerging solutions where possible.

Word count SEC43 (max. 250): 213

4.4 Budget

Position	HOT scale	Institution	Total FTE	Years active	Amount
Project manager	X	EMC	2,00	4	X
Research software engineer		EMC	2,00	2	
Research software engineer		EMC	3,00	3	
Research software engineer		UvA	2,00	2	
Senior research software engineer		EMC	0,40	2	
Senior research software engineer		EMC	0,60	3	
Senior research software engineer		EMC	0,40	2	
Assistant professor		EMC	0,40	4	
Assistant professor		EMC	0,40	4	
Postdoc		EMC	0,40	4	
Postdoc	EMC	0,40	4		

Material/IT Type	Description	Cost calculation	Total (€)
(international) travel and accommodation expenses incl. conference visit	Attendance project manager and software developers at ARVO (international conference)	2,000 per conference x 2 yrs x 3p	€ 12.000,00
(international) travel and accommodation expenses incl. conference visit	Attendance project manager and software developers at NOG (national conference)	300 per conference x 4yrs x 3p	€ 3.600,00
(international) travel and accommodation expenses incl. conference visit	Travel cost to install software and organize workshops at local centres	4 centres x 4 visits x 2 people x 50e	€ 1.600,00
work performed by third parties	Legal expert	80 hours at 125e	€ 10.000,00
costs of data management for this project	Local IT support for setting up ETL pipelines	40 hours x 4 centers x 75e	€ 12.000,00
work performed by third parties	SURF cloud consultancy	80 hours x 139e	€ 11.120,00
Consumables (only during infra setup, not for use and maintenance)	Storage and compute for development and testing	1TB block storage 4 year (SURF)	€ 10.332,00

Total Personnel requested: 1.434.132,00

Total Material/IT requested: 60.652,00

Total budget requested: 1.494.784,00

4.5 Budget justification

- **Project manager (0.5 FTE for 5 years)**

The project manager will coordinate, organize outreach activities (T4.3) and manage the development of the legal agreements and sustainability plan (WP5).

- **Research software engineers (3x) (1.0 FTE 7 years total)**

Fulltime research software engineer (RSE) will be hired to develop and extend the software. They will be embedded in teams with expertise on the existing infrastructure components.

- **Senior research software engineers (3x) (0.2 FTE 7 years total)**

For each RSE, a senior RSE will be assigned for 0.2 FTE to supervise the development.

- **Assistant professors (2x0.1 FTE 4 years) and postdoc researchers (2x0.1 FTE 4 years)**

Four researchers will be assigned .1 FTE to test the infrastructure and provide feedback to the developers. These will onboard the clinics and cohorts in tasks 4.1 and 4.2 and act as ambassadors for the infrastructure in task 4.3.

- **Conference attendance ARVO**

Participation in this conference is essential to reach international collaborators and commercial parties.

- **Conference attendance NOG**

Participation in NOG is essential to reach (potential) users and we will organize yearly workshops to showcase our tools.

- **Legal expert**

We will hire a legal expert to draft the consortium agreement in task 5.1.

- **Local IT support**

To install the ETL pipelines developed in WP 1 will require assistance from local IT departments.

- **SURF cloud consultancy**

Advice from SURF will be sought to help with the cloud implementation in WP 2.

- **Storage and compute**

Costs for storage and compute will be carried by users of the infrastructure, but an initial budget is needed to support development and testing.

Own contributions:

- **Supervision Klaver, Klein and Sanchez**

- **EyeNED Reading Centre grading:** Graders at the EyeNED Reading Centre will perform the grading in task 4.2.

Word count SEC45 (max. 300): 284

4.6 Impact plan

There will be immediate impact on research by providing a PACS with multimodal annotation and curation capabilities not available in clinical systems. Access to AI algorithms will further accelerate both clinical and technical research. High-quality data generated in these projects will be FAIR by design, achieving additional impact through reuse in other projects. We maximise this impact by onboarding data during the project, visiting individual centres and showcasing our tools at conferences.

To ensure impact beyond academia, we will enable responsible data sharing with commercial parties through our technical and legal framework. Companies depend on clinical data to develop and validate their algorithms, and this infrastructure supports such collaborations by removing technical and legal barriers. We will also promote wider adoption of open standards by engaging with manufacturers and their user communities, highlighting where compliance can be improved.

In society, we achieve long-term impact by supporting research based on representative clinical data—reducing bias and increasing trust. We ensure patient data is reused responsibly and securely. This will result in better patient care at lower cost.

Figure 8. Schematic overview of impact.

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 190

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

This project will deliver three main outcomes that require sustainability: 1) open-source software, 2) cloud infrastructure and 3) a consortium agreement.

1. Open-source software

The open-source software will require updates and maintenance to remain functional, requiring personnel with sufficient expertise. Elements of the ETL pipelines will need to be updated with developments in modalities, devices and standards in the field. The EyeNED platform and its integration with other systems will require maintenance as issues may arise over time.

The ETL pipelines will be designed in a modular and extensible way so that individual components can be replaced or updated over time. The open standards are not expected to change, therefore providing a solid foundation for the pipelines. Data ingestion from commercial systems is more prone to changes that are beyond our control. We will provide transparent documentation so that future updates can be made by users and manufacturers if needed.

The EyeNED platform has already been developed from project-based funding at the Erasmus MC (EyeNED Reading Centre), and it forms an integral part of our operations. The Moorfields Reading Centre has joined the effort to use and develop the platform. As multiple research groups with relevant expertise rely on this software, we are confident that the maintenance will be continued beyond this project. Making the software open source will potentially expand the user community and attract other groups to contribute to its maintenance. We will explore options for structural funding from research institutes or charities, in discussion with the Dutch Ophthalmology Society ([NOG](#)) and Health-RI.

2. Cloud services

The expansion of the central Health-RI medical imaging cloud infrastructure with the research PACS and algorithm integration forms an integral part of the outcomes of this work. This infrastructure is hosted and managed through Health-RI, a national non-profit organization supported by all Dutch university medical centres. Sustainability of this infrastructure depends on financial resources for cloud hosting, system administration, and user support. The costs for cloud services are covered by the fees charged to users of the infrastructure.

We partner with the Lifelong Vision consortium to be early adopters of the cloud service, and they commit to carrying the associated costs for the duration of the project (until 2034). This provides a strong foundation for sustainability in the first decade. Outreach activities during the project will attract additional users, supporting financial continuity beyond that point.

3. Consortium agreement

The consortium agreement will need to be renegotiated or updated in the future. Some elements may become outdated or obsolete with the implementation of EHDS, which we will monitor during the project. We are confident that the participating institutes will reach a new agreement if there is a continued need for it.

Word count SEC51 (450): 448

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

Our software consists of two key components:

- **ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) Pipelines:** A set of scripts and software components that extract imaging data from local clinical systems, transform it into a standardized, vendor-neutral format, send it to a vendor-neutral database.
- **EyeNED platform:** A web-based client designed for viewing and annotating ophthalmic imaging, coupled to a database system for annotations. The underlying software is linked to other systems within the Health-RI

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ecosystem through API calls.

The intended audience is researchers working with ophthalmic imaging data, including reading centers, as well as technical researchers developing algorithms for ophthalmic imaging.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

We will use the Git version control system along with an online Git-based code repository (e.g., GitHub or GitLab). Versioning will follow semantic versioning (e.g., v1.0.0), with major updates packaged as releases. When applicable, stable versions will be made available via a package index (e.g., PyPI for Python-based components).

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

All software is or will be publicly available through a Git-based repository (e.g., GitHub or GitLab) and distributed via package indices where relevant. The licensing structure will be as follows:

- **ETL Pipelines:** Licensed under the **Apache License 2.0 License**, ensuring flexibility for modification and redistribution.
- **EyeNED platform:** Licensed under the **GNU General Public License (GPL)**, ensuring that modifications remain open-source and benefit the broader community.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

we will provide a citation format in the repository's README file and documentation. We will use Zenodo to generate a DOI or publish an article describing the software in a journal that support such publications, such as the [TVST Data Science](#) track.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

We will provide comprehensive documentation, including:

- Step-by-step installation instructions. For the EyeNED platform installation is possible through docker-compose. Dependencies, and system requirements will be documented in an INSTALL.md file and package manager configurations (e.g., requirements.txt for Python).
- A user manual explaining configuration, and usage, available as a README file in the repository and hosted on a documentation platform (e.g., Read the Docs).
- A user manual for the PACS embedded within in the web interface
- Developer documentation outlining the underlying functionality and code structure.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

Contribution guidelines will be documented in a **CONTRIBUTING.md** file to maintain a general structure in the software and ensure consistent practices. This will also include guidelines on how to submit issues and bug reports. The groups carrying the main development effort will also be in the lead in terms of the decision-making process for updates and new features.

7. How will your software be tested?

Testing of the software consists of several layers:

- Unit tests for functionality of critical components, that run automatically in a CI/CD pipeline.
- Integration tests using test data to ensure workflows remain functional.
- Manual testing of the interface as the software is constantly in use.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

We will review dependencies manually and through automated license checkers (e.g., pip-licenses, license-checker) to verify that all included libraries align with our open-source licenses.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

The software will be packaged and distributed through:

- **Public Git Repositories** (e.g., GitHub, GitLab)
- **Package Indexes** (e.g., PyPI) where applicable
- **Docker Images** to run the software locally or in the cloud.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

- **Health-RI support:** Users accessing cloud services via Health-RI will receive support through the Health-RI service desk, which will escalate technical issues to developers if needed.
- **Open-Source Community Support:** General users can report issues via the public code repository, where developers and contributors will address them.
- **Documentation:** A dedicated section in the documentation will cover common issues and troubleshooting steps.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

The sustainability of the software is ensured by:

- **Institutional Commitment:** The developing institutions (Erasmus MC, Moorfields Reading Centre) rely on the software for their research, ensuring continued maintenance and updates. The Lifelong Vision consortium also commits to using the software throughout the project (10 years).
- **Open-Source Community:** By promoting the use of our software internationally, other groups can help maintain and improve the software over time.
- **Funding & Partnerships:** Future funding applications will support ongoing development and infrastructure hosting.

Section 6: References

1. Pandit, R. R., & Boland, M. V. (2015). Impact of Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine Workflow on the Integration of Patient Demographics and Ophthalmic Test Data. *Ophthalmology*, 122(2), 227–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ophtha.2014.08.036>
2. Shweikh, Y., Sekimitsu, S., Boland, M. V., & Zebardast, N. (2022). The growing need for ophthalmic data standardization. *Ophthalmology Science*, 2(4), Article 100262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xops.2022.100262>
3. Goetz, K. E., Boland, M. V., Chu, Z., et al. (2024). Ocular imaging challenges, current state, and a path to interoperability: A HIMSS-SIIM enterprise imaging community whitepaper. *Journal of Imaging Informatics in Medicine*, 1–10.
4. AI-READI Consortium. (2024). Flagship Dataset of Type 2 Diabetes from the AI-READI Project (Version 2.0.0) [Data set]. FAIRhub. <https://doi.org/10.60775/fairhub.2>
5. Parrish, R. S., Goetz, K. E., & Tumminia, S. J. (2018). eyeGENE®: A Model for Advancing Research of Rare, Inherited Eye Conditions Through Biobanking and Data Sharing. In *Advances in Vision Research, Volume II* (pp. 29–39). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-0884-0_4

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.